

Harmful phytoplankton species recorded during a survey near the submarine outfall discharges of the Seaflower Biosphere Reserve

Fig. 1. San Andrés Island showing submarine outfall discharges and sampling site.

The island of San Andrés, located in the Colombian Caribbean, is part of the Seaflower Biosphere Reserve, which was designated by UNESCO in 2000. Due to its scenic beauty and high biodiversity, San Andrés is a major tourist attraction, receiving annually an estimated one million visitors of various nationalities, representing 60% of the island's GDP. However, the island is also characterized by its high vulnerability, being small (27 km²), oceanic (110 km offshore), and densely populated (2,000 inhabitants/km²) [1]. The island also faces extreme weather events such as Hurricane Iota, a Category 4 storm that struck the archipelago in November 2020 [2]. In addition, precarious management of natural resources is compromising the environmental quality of its ecosystems.

One measure adopted to improve domestic wastewater management — identified as one of the island's main sanitation problems — was the construction of a submarine outfall to collect domestic and hotel wastewater from the northern sector; the most densely populated part of the island, in 2007 (Fig. 1). The outfall discharges

untreated wastewater at a depth of only 18 m [3]. After nearly two decades of operation, changes in water transparency and odor near the discharge point are evident.

To assess the potential effects of the submarine outfall on coastal waters of San Andrés Island, plankton sampling was conducted at three depths. Samples were collected in duplicate during the rainy season approximately 1 km offshore within the discharge zone. Surface samples were obtained using subsurface circular tows with a 20 µm mesh net. Samples from depths of 0, 10 and 20 m were collected using a 5 L Niskin bottle and subsequently concentrated by passing them through a 20 µm mesh net. All samples were fixed with 10% formalin and analyzed using an Olympus CK2 inverted phase contrast microscope, using the 40x objective. Results were compared with historical records from previous years and from different sampling locations around San Andrés.

Among the 62 morphotypes identified, five species and three genera are listed as toxic, and seven species and one genus as harmful, according to the

IOC-UNESCO HAB Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae [4]. Fifteen of these are new records for San Andrés (Table 1). Although plankton sampling does not allow a causal link to be established between outfall discharges and the presence of toxic and harmful non-toxic taxa, the detection of previously unreported species in a single survey is noteworthy.

Point-source discharge of wastewater from the outfall — serving roughly one-third of households in the island's northwest sector — has been associated with increased concentrations of total inorganic nitrogen in coastal waters. Adverse impacts on western reef systems, including coral diseases, proliferation of microalgae and sponges, and detection of the fecal indicator *Escherichia coli* in coral mucus, have been linked to exposure to wastewater from the outfall and other diffuse sources [5]. These findings highlight the need to re-establish a plankton monitoring program to improve early detection of HAB events. San Andrés is also notable for recurrent ciguatera cases [6], which are uncommon along the continental Caribbean coast of Colombia.

HAB events associated with coastal pollution not only pose risks to public health but also reduce the ecosystem and cultural services provided by the island. Because these impacts are not always apparent to decision-makers, dissemination of information should form part of an early warning strategy [7].

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Table 1. Potentially Toxic and Harmful Non-Toxic Species Reported from the Waters Surrounding San Andrés Island.

Type	Taxon name	Associated Toxins
Potentially Toxic	<i>Coolia malayensis</i> Leaw, P.-T.Lim & Usup, 2001	Yessotoxin analogues
	<i>Gambierdiscus caribaeus</i> Vandersea, Litaker, M.A.Faust, Kibler, W.C.Holland & P.A.Tester, 2009	44-methylgambierone, C-CTX5
	<i>Lyngbya majuscula</i> Harvey ex Gomont, 1892	Lyngbyatoxins, Debromoaplysiatoxin, Aplysiatoxin
	<i>Prorocentrum concavum</i> Y.Fukuyo, 1981	OA, OA diol ester, DTX-1, fast acting toxins (FAT)
	<i>Prorocentrum hoffmannianum</i> M.A.Faust, 1990	Okadaic acid, fast acting toxins (FAT)
	<i>Coolia</i> sp. Meunier, 1919	Yessotoxin analogues
	<i>Phormidium</i> sp. Kützing ex Gomont, 1892	Cyanotoxins
	<i>Trichodesmium</i> sp. Ehrenberg ex Gomont, 1892	Microcystins, Palytoxin (PLTX) and 42-OH-PLTX, Saxitoxins, CTX-like
Potentially Harmful non-toxic	<i>Coscinodiscus concinnus</i> W.Smith, 1856	
	<i>Cylindrotheca closterium</i> (Ehrenberg) Reimann & J.C.Lewin, 1964	
	<i>Chaetoceros wighamii</i> Brightwell, 1856	
	<i>Protoperidinium depressum</i> (Bailey, 1854) Balech, 1974	
	<i>Tripos furca</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Gómez, 2013	
	<i>Tripos lineatus</i> (Ehrenberg) F.Gómez, 2013	
	<i>Tripos muelleri</i> Bory de Saint-Vincent, 1826	
	<i>Rhizosolenia</i> sp. T. Brightwell, 1858	

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